

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DELINQUENT BEHAVIOUR AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF PUBLIC SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN NORTH-CENTRAL, NIGERIA

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Delinquency, Academic Performance, Secondary Education, Student Behaviour, Nigeria

Abstract: *The study examined the relationship between delinquent behaviour and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in North-Central, Nigeria. Four objectives, two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive-correlational research design was employed for the study. The population of the study comprised of 685,795 public senior secondary school students in North-Central, Nigeria, with a sample size of 396. Simple random sampling technique was used for the study. A researcher structured questionnaire was used for data collection. A pilot test was conducted to establish the reliability of the questionnaire, which yielded reliability index of 0.86. The data collected was analyzed using mean scores and standard deviation for to answer the research questions, while Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) and independent sample t-test Analysis were used to test the hypotheses. The findings revealed that students exhibited delinquent behaviours such as drug abuse, violating school rules, creating disturbance in the classroom, throwing dangerous weapons at peers, deceitfulness and theft amongst. The findings also revealed a no significant relationship between delinquent behaviour and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in North-Central, Nigeria. The findings equally revealed a significant difference between male and female students' delinquent behaviours on their academic performance. Based on the findings, it was recommended that government at all levels should provide adequate learning materials, functional and conducive learning environment in order to enable students learn well and abide by school rules and regulation.*

INTRODUCTION

Delinquency is basically a legal concept, defined in different ways among people or scholars. It is

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defined as a state of being delinquent or a behaviour manifested by adolescents that is not in accordance with accepted social standards or with societal norms. In a society, a delinquent behaviour could refer to any act committed majorly by adolescents which could be detrimental to the individual and significant others, and also punishable by law. It is mostly the product of social and economic conditions which is essentially a co-efficient of the friction between the individual involved and the community. Delinquent behavior is an act when commitment could affect others not directly involved and the larger society. Siegal et al. (2021) stressed that juvenile delinquency is the participation in illegal behaviour by minors (individuals younger than the statutory age of majority). It is the antisocial, illegal or criminal behaviour perpetuated by children or adolescents to the level that it cannot be controlled or corrected by the parents, therefore endangers others in the society and becomes the concern of law enforcement agency. The term juvenile delinquency was established so that law breakers could avoid the disgrace of being classified in illegal records as criminals.

Dodge (2017) asserts that delinquent behaviour is a disruptive type of behaviour in which a child routinely violates the personal rights of others and shows no care for others property. The view of Dodge is also supported by Baker and Scarth (2017) who emphasized that delinquent

behaviour are persistent pattern of antisocial behaviour in which the rights of others are violated or in which major social rules are broken. A juvenile delinquent in Nigeria is a person who is typically under the age of nineteen and commits an act that otherwise could have been charged as a crime if they were adults. Delinquent behaviors may include theft, gambling, pick-pocketing, cheating, destroying properties, selling drugs, burglary, robbery, vandalism, kidnapping, self-arm, school absenteeism physical aggression, rape & smoking of marijuana and assault. The delinquent offenders are usually below 18 years. Delinquents are viewed as individuals who come from less intact families, often referred to as “broken homes. When parents abdicate their roles and fail with their responsibilities to mould and inculcate in their children the right norms, etiquette, values and belief system that are generally accepted within the society, the young adults become dangerous specie to the society manifesting alien, pervasive and uncultured behaviours such as truancy, restiveness, drug abuse, kidnapping, banditry, armed robbery, cultism and fraud amongst others (Gidado & Diffang, 2023).

Delinquency itself is socially inadequate adjustment on the part of the individual to difficult situations. Mental and physical conditions which influence an individual's capacity to adjust, could constitute the causes of

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delinquency. Each juvenile offense is the outcome of a complexity of causes, some whose origins date back years before the committal of the offense and others whose origins are more obviously and immediately connected with the act of delinquency. Shehu and Ngwoke (2017) revealed that at age 14, most delinquent conduct involves minor theft. By age 16 or 17, more violent and dangerous acts, including assault and the used of weapon, become prevalent.

The rising incidence of child delinquency in many countries may be caused by certain socio-economic problems often associated with development. Many psychologists struggle with the continuous nature versus nurture debate when it comes to delinquency in children. Some think is biological, suggesting that the children were born with it and that they inherited some type of illness from their parents. Others believe that delinquent behaviour could be a product of their environment and that they act out and kill people due to social pressures, abuse, and neglect they have faced in their lives. Children who live in the home with only one parent or in which marital relationship have been disrupted by divorce or separation are more likely to display a range of behavioural problems including delinquency, than children who have two parent families (Thombery & Solomon, 2019). It has long been a problem why some children steal and others do not, why some play truant, or why some set fires and damage

property. Officers of the juvenile courts, child welfare associations, educational bodies, and mental hygiene clinics have been instrumental in bringing together a vast amount of data concerning child delinquency, from which certain general conclusions may be drawn.

Various researchers have reported different reasons for delinquency (Gidado & Diffang, 2024; Gidado & Zubair, 2025). Therefore, the relationship between parents' socioeconomic status and delinquency cannot be over emphasized. Students from high socioeconomic backgrounds enjoyed better living conditions (Osokoya, 2017). That is, they are provided with the necessary thing of life such as good food, proper clothing, decent and comfortable accommodation, and other facilities to aid them in their academic achievement. Students from middle class are fairly provided with the above facilities that can also promote academic performance. But, on the other hand, students from low economic background are provided with little or none of these facilities or materials mentioned above of which lack of it, would lead to students performing below expectation and thereby going into delinquent behaviours in order to survive (Osokoya, 2017). The way parents nurture, discipline, and communicate with their children has a direct impact on their aggression and hostility levels (Gidado & Anyio, 2025).

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Some delinquent children may be products of low socio-economic background which may have psychological impact on their behaviour. According to Moffitt (2016), there are two different types of offenders that emerge in adolescence. One is the repeat offender, referred to as the life-course-persistent offender, who begins offending or showing antisocial/aggressive behaviour in adolescence and continues into adulthood; and the age specific offender, referred to as the adolescence-limited offender, for whom juvenile offending or delinquency begins and ends during their period of adolescence. Because most teenagers tend to show some form of antisocial, aggressive or delinquent behaviour during adolescence, it is important to account for these behaviours in childhood in order to determine whether they will be life-course-persistent offenders or adolescence-limited offenders. Although adolescence-limited offenders tend to drop all criminal activities once they enter into adulthood and show less pathology than life-course-persistent offenders, they still show more mental health, substance abuse, and finance problems, both in adolescence and adulthood, than those who were never delinquent.

It could be observed in some of our public senior secondary schools in North-central, Nigeria that there exist students who perpetuate different juvenile delinquent related acts. Some students

are known for going late to school, abusing of illicit substances that should not be ingested at their age, bullying, stealing, indulging into fraudulent related activities which could all have detrimental consequences to their general well-being and also influence their academic performance.

Academic performance is the quality and quantity of knowledge, skills, techniques and positive attitudes, behaviours and idea that students achieve or acquire. This achievement is weighed up by the marks or grade that students make in a form or education cycle. Academic performance has a great impact on a student's motivation, confidence and determination in education. It is the measurement of students' achievement across various academic subjects, (Rono, 2019). Teachers and education officials typically measure using classroom performance, graduation rates and result from standardized tests. He also seen academic performance of students is a key feature in education. It is considered to be the centre around which the education system revolves. Academic performance is the knowledge gained which is assessed by marks by a teacher or educational goals set by students and teachers to be achieved over a specific period of time. Academic performance of students determines the success or failure of any academic institution. James (2020) declared that academic performance involves how much students has learned. It is

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also view as the outcome of education, the extent to which a student, teacher and institution has achieved their educational goal.

Studies have shown how delinquency could be synonymous with students' academic performance either negatively or positively. Students' unruly behaviour has constantly affected school academic achievement to the extent that teachers are unable to cover the contents of the school curriculum and this often result into producing half-baked graduates (Fareo, 2019). Aladejana (2020) revealed that there was no significant connection between delinquent behaviour and students' academic performance in mathematics. However, Ikediashi (2010) indicated a significant difference between delinquent and non-delinquent students' and their academic achievement. Non-delinquent students performed better than delinquent students even without treatment. Children and adolescents who are aggressive are also more likely to struggle in school, perform poorly academically, and drop out, which can lead to lack of employment options, weaker ability to adjust to working life, long-term unemployment, and social marginalization (Fairchild et al., 2019). Okuegbu and Fadimpe (2016) asserted that non-delinquent students performed better than delinquent students even when taught together. There was higher level of delinquency among the older juvenile than the younger ones. The

academic performance of delinquent students improved after been taught.

Gender seems to be a factor in the relationship between delinquent behaviour and academic performance of students. According to Lau and Leung (2018) gender differences were found in respondents' deviant behaviour whereby male respondents were more likely to verbally attack teachers, bully, and vandalise school properties while female respondents were found to be more likely to verbally attack parents, as opposed to teachers. Gidado (2021) indicated that no significant sex difference was observed in all the courses analysed at the .05 level except in the continuous assessment scores of HIS 102 (Foundation of Nigeria History II) which revealed a sex difference with $P \leq 0.001$. Since adolescents may not witness peers challenging their parents at home, their self-esteem could remain relatively low since it may not be enhanced as a result. What is difficult to define is whether delinquent adolescents affiliate with delinquent friends, or whether delinquent friends produces delinquent adolescents (Fergusson, 2017). The enhancement of young people's self-esteem (gaining peer attention) through engaging in deviant behaviour is more significant and is an important factor in their susceptibility to peer influence and rebelliousness. This mechanism acts as a vicious cycle for delinquents (Streit, 2018). Which could

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obviously have tremendous negative impact on students' academic performance.

Some studies show minimal or no significant relationship between delinquent behaviour and academic performance while others reported high or positive relationships. The contextual socioeconomic background in North-Central Nigeria where most children seems to be from rural area which could be an indicator of their socioeconomic background and may influence the relationship contrarily compared to children from middle or high socioeconomic background. It is against this background that the research work will examine relationship between delinquent behaviour and academic performance of public senior secondary students in North-central, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

There seems to be an alarming rate of delinquent behaviour among students in public senior secondary schools in North-central, Nigeria which could have adverse effect on their academic performance. While socio-emotional and psychological stability could enhance students' academic performance especially when their sociopsychological needs are met, deprivation, isolation, rejection among others could negatively correlate with students' psychological stability and lead to poor academic performance.

It is worrisome to note that students tend to face a lot of emotional and psychological problems

arising from irregular school attendance, lack of personal and interpersonal skills to cope with school works which may constitute a cause for grave concern to parents, teachers, students, examination bodies, counselors, psychologists and the government. Delinquents suffers from deprivation, isolation, rejection, unassertiveness and poor performance which is due to their inability to cope with social cognitive and problem-solving skills. Some parents neither assist their children in the home work or assignment nor participate in the school related programmes such parents do not monitor the progress of their children hence, abdicates their responsibility to school teachers. Secondary school students in North Central, Nigeria are lured into engaging in negative habits such as excessive drinking of alcohol, smoking of Indian hemp, cultist related activities, violent school demonstration, vandalism, engagement in unhealthy sexual behaviour, bullying, use of substances abuse, arm robbery, sexual assault and other maladjusted behaviours that distract them from academic pursuit, and also lead to poor academic performance in schools. Statistics, data from west Africa Examination council (WAEC) 2022 have been recording massive failure, not only in overall performance of the students, but also in core subjects like English, Mathematics and sciences (i.e Biology, Physics, Chemistry) for instance, the performance of

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students in WAEC May/June 2019-2023: Showed that Mathematics in 2019 have 41.95%, in 2020 have 54.02%, in 2021 have 50.14%, in 2022 have 34.02% and in 2023 have 56.14% have credits While in English Language in 2019 have 25.09%, in 2020 44.32%, in 2021 have 19.35%, in 2022 have 19.65%, 2023 17.42% have credit. (Nigeria Bureau of Statistics, 2023) in North-central States is disturbing and embarrassing for the above poor performance of Students in WAEC.

It is against this backdrop that the researcher investigates relationship between delinquent behaviour and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this research was to examine the relationship between delinquent behaviour and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

1. Find out the delinquent behaviours common among students of public senior secondary schools in North-Central, Nigeria.
2. Examine the academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Mathematics, English Language, Biology and Economics in North-Central, Nigeria.
3. Determine the relationship between delinquents behaviour and academic

performance among students of public senior secondary schools in North-Central, Nigeria.

4. Examine the difference on the impact of delinquent behaviour and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in North-Central, Nigeria in respective of gender.

Research Question

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What are the delinquent behaviours common among students of public senior secondary schools in North-Central, Nigeria?
2. What is the academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Mathematics, English Language, Biology and Economics in North-Central, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between delinquent behaviour and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in North-Central, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference on the impact of delinquent behaviour on academic performance of public senior secondary school students in North-Central, Nigeria in respective of gender.

METHODOLOGY

Design

The research design employed in this study was descriptive-correlational survey. Descriptive survey assists the researcher in gathering and

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interpreting data descriptively without influencing the data. Correlation survey design aims at identifying predictive relationship among two or more variables. Correlational design is a study design for examining the relationships between or among two or more variables in a single group, which can occur at several levels (Barkha et al., 2022).

Population

The population of this study comprised all public senior secondary school students in North-Central Nigeria. There are 685,795 public senior secondary school students in North-Central Nigeria (Secondary Education Board (SEB, 2023) spread across six States with the FCT. The states include Benue, F.C.T Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Niger and Plateau. Out of the total population of students, four hundred and fifty-six thousand, five hundred and ninety-five (456,595) are male while two hundred and twenty-nine thousand and two hundred (229,200) are female.

Sample Size and Procedure

The study used a sample size of 396 students which was determined using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table for determining sample size for specific population. A multi – stage sampling procedure was adopted for this study. At the first stage, simple random technique was used to select eight (8) public senior secondary schools drawn from each of the seven (7) States in North – Central Nigeria, making a total of

fifty-six (56) schools. Simple random sampling technique was also used to select the respondents from each of the selected schools in North – Central Nigeria.

Instrumentation

The research instrument in this study was a self-developed questionnaire, titled; Delinquent Behaviour of Senior Secondary School Students Questionnaire (DBSSSSQ). The questionnaire was structured in accordance with the four points Likert Scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD) SA = 4, A = 3, D = 2 and SD.

The instrument was validated for face and content validity with a reliability index of 0.86 by experts in measurement and evaluation at the University of Abuja.

Students' academic records in the National Examination Council (NECO) for 2019 -2023 was also used to determine their academic performance.

Method of Data Analysis

Data collected was analyze using descriptive and inferential statistics. Mean scores and standard deviation was used to analyze the research questions while Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) and independent sampled t-test were used to test the hypotheses.

Results

Research Question One: What are the delinquent behaviours common among students

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of public senior secondary schools in North-Central, Nigeria?

Table 1: Delinquent behaviours of students of public senior secondary schools

S/No.	Items	Mean	Std Dev.	Decision
1	I enjoy smoking Indian hemp during school hour	2.74	0.92	Agree
2	I always drink alcohol	2.30	0.99	Agree
3	I often use of substance abuse	2.82	0.87	Agree
4	I often vandalize school properties	2.44	0.92	Disagree
5	Always engaging in unhealthy sexual behaviour	2.53	0.99	Agree
6	I always involve arm robbery	2.65	0.87	Disagree
7	I involve in deceitfulness and theft	2.99	1.01	Agree
8	I am always curious to exhibit deviant behaviour	2.54	1.05	Disagree
9	I am always frustrated and depressed	2.76	0.90	Agree
10	My parents lack moral conduct	2.65	0.46	Agree
11	I always take illicit drugs	3.00	1.89	Agree
12	I always steal something in my teacher's car	2.37	0.77	Disagree
13	I always like fighting in school	2.64	0.91	Agree
14	I always been maltreated	2.85	0.80	Agree
15	My environment lacks moral values	2.39	0.23	Agree
16	I feel like damaging school properties	2.45	0.47	Agree
17	I find it difficult to attack someone with intent to harm	3.26	0.52	Agree
18	I always cheat at examination hall	2.27	0.77	Agree
19	I often created a disturbance or disorderly in classroom	3.16	0.65	Agree
20	I always throw things (bottles, knife, bag etc) at peers	3.57	0.69	Agree
Sectional Mean/Std. Mean		2.83	0.83	Agree

As shown in table 1, the delinquent behaviours among students of public senior secondary schools in North-Central, was presented. The overall sectional means of 2.83, indicates that students violate school rules and moral conduct

including deceitfulness and theft during classroom learning. A total of sixteen (16) items revealed agreement while four (4) items indicated disagreement. This implies that students exhibit delinquent behaviours during

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school hours, as they engage in disruptive behaviour in classroom learning.

Research Question Two: What is the academic performance of public senior

secondary school students in Mathematics, English Language, Biology and Economics in North-Central, Nigeria

Table 2: Academic performance of senior secondary school students in Mathematics, English Language, Biology and Economics

	Minimum	Maximum	Average Score
Mathematics	23.00	54.00	60.32
English Language	5.00	65.00	59.54
Biology	48.00	90.00	60.08
Economics	17.00	86.00	52.43
Academic Performance	38.50	81.00	60.03

Source; NECO, Internal Examination, 2019 ----2023

As shown in table 2, the academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Mathematics, English Language, Biology and Economics in North-Central, Nigeria was presented. The table show a minimum score 23.00 for mathematics while the maximum score was 54.00 with an average score of 60.32. As for English Language, the table revealed a minimum score of 5.00, with a maximum of 65.00 and an average score of 59.54.’ As for Biology, the table revealed a minimum score of 48.00, with a maximum score of 90.00 and an average score of 60.08. As for Economics, the table revealed a minimum of 17.00, with a

maximum of 86.00 and an average score of 52.43. The overall academic performance of public senior secondary school students in North-Central, Nigeria shows a minimum of 38.50, with a maximum of 81.00 and average of 60.03. Therefore, the average score of 60.03 is above 50 midpoint which indicates that overall academic performance of students is above average.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between delinquent behaviour and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in North-Central, Nigeria.

Table 3: Correlational Analysis between delinquent behaviour and academic performance of public senior secondary school students

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	r-cal	p-value	Decision
Delinquent Behaviour and	396	3.00	.44	.674	.071	Accepted

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Academic Performance

Correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2-tailed) PPMC

As shown in table 3, a correlational analysis to determine the relationship between delinquent behaviour and academic performance of public senior secondary school students was presented. The table revealed a mean of 3.00 and a standard deviation of 0.44 with an r value of .674. The table further revealed p-value of 0.000, with $p > 0.05$. This implies that there is no significant relationship between delinquent

behaviour and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in North-Central, Nigeria. The hypothesis was therefore retained.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference on the impact of delinquent behaviour on academic performance of public senior secondary school students in North-Central, Nigeria in respective of gender.

Table 4: t-test Analysis in the male and female students' delinquent behaviour and academic performance

Gender	N	Mean	S.D	t-value	df	Sig (2-tailed)	Decision
Male	215	2.67	1.88	2.92	394	0.000	Rejected
Female	181	3.10	0.27				

Correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2-tailed) PPMC

As shown in table 4, an independent sampled t-test analysis to determine the difference on the impact of delinquent behaviour and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in respective of gender was presented. The table revealed a mean of 2.67 with a standard deviation of 1.88 for male students and a mean of 3.10 with a standard deviation of 0.27 for female students. The table further revealed a table value of 0.000 which less than $p < 0.05$. This implies that there is significant difference in male and female students' delinquent behaviour on academic performance of public senior secondary school students in North-Central, Nigeria.

Discussions

The findings revealed that students exhibited delinquent behaviours such as drug abuse,

violating school rules, creating disturbance in the classroom, throwing dangerous weapons (bottles, knife, bag etc) at peers, deceitfulness, and theft amongst others. This is corroborated by Shehu and Ngwoke (2017) who revealed that at age 14, most delinquent conduct involves minor theft. By age 16 or 17, more violent and dangerous acts, including assault and the used of weapon, become prevalent. Similarly, Dodge (2017) revealed that delinquent behaviour is a disruptive type of behaviour in which a child routinely violates the personal rights of others and shows no care for others property. The view of Dodge is also supported by Baker and Scarth (2021) who emphasized that delinquent behaviour are persistent pattern of antisocial behaviour in which the rights of others are violated or in which major social rules are

broken. Gidado and Diffang (2023) asserted that when parents abdicate their roles and fail with their responsibilities to mould and inculcate in their children the right norms, etiquette, values and belief system that are generally accepted within the society, the young adults become dangerous specie to the society manifesting alien, pervasive and uncultured behaviours such as truancy, restiveness, drug abuse, kidnapping, banditry, armed robbery, cultism and fraud amongst others.

The findings showed that the academic performance of public senior secondary school students is above average. This is in line with Oludipe (2015) who revealed that the general academic achievement of male and female students was above average. Also, Nwachukwu (2018) reported that exposing students to small group cooperative interaction learning style makes them attain high cognitive performance. Williams (2019) equally reported that there was no significant difference between the performance of male and female students since their performances were above average.

The findings also revealed no significant relationship between delinquent behaviour and academic performance of public senior secondary school students. This is supported by Aladejana (2020) who revealed that there was no significant connection between delinquent behaviour and students' academic performance in mathematics. However, the finding is contrary with Ikediashi (2010) who indicated a significant difference between delinquent and non-delinquent students' and their academic

achievement. Ikediashi further asserted that non-delinquent students performed better than delinquent students even without treatment. Okuegbu and Fadinpe (2016) also asserted that non-delinquent students performed better than delinquent students even when taught together. There was higher level of delinquency among the older juvenile than the younger ones. The academic performance of delinquent students improved after been taught.

The findings revealed a significant difference on the impact of delinquent behaviour on academic performance of public senior secondary school students in respective of gender. This is in accordance with Rathod and Chauhan (2023) who revealed that there was significant relationship between gender difference and academic performance among primary school in Gujarati. Similarly, Lau and Leung (2016) also revealed that poor relation with school had a more negative effect on the self-concept of girls than boys, and a more negative impact on the delinquency of boys. However, Gidado (2021) indicated that no significant sex difference was observed in all the courses analysed at the .05 level except in the continuous assessment scores of HIS 102 (Foundation of Nigeria History II) which revealed a sex difference with $P \leq 0.001$.

Conclusion

This study investigated the relationship between delinquent behaviour and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in North-Central, Nigeria. It has been observed that students exhibit delinquent behaviour during school hours, as they engage

in disruptive behaviour in classroom learning. It therefore concluded that delinquent behaviour influences academic performance of senior secondary school students in North-Central, Nigeria.

Recommendations

1. Government should establish three positive skills, moral reasoning and social skills in public secondary schools to curb and eradicate delinquent behaviour while also, censor the types of information published on media.
2. Government at all levels should provide adequate learning materials, functional and conducive learning environment should be

provided in order to enable students learn well and the abide school rules and regulations.

3. Psychologist should endeavor to explore the effectiveness of other behavioural modification techniques on delinquent behaviour of children and adolescents
4. Parents should introduce cordial relationship with their children at all levels of developmental stages especially adolescence (male and female), as the home being the first basic social functioning unit, a significant agent of socialization and education. A malfunctioning background can pre-dispose a child either male or female to future delinquent behaviour (truancy).

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